

DATA-DRIVEN FLUTTER PREDICTION FOR AXIAL COMPRESSORS USING DEEP LEARNING MODELS

Judith Kraus
PhD Candidate
Chair of Aero Engines
Technische Universität Berlin
Berlin, Germany

Mario Eck
PostDoc
Chair of Aero Engines
Technische Universität Berlin
Berlin, Germany

Dieter Peitsch
Professor
Chair of Aero Engines
Technische Universität Berlin
Berlin, Germany

ABSTRACT

Flutter is a critical aeroelastic instability that can possibly lead to structural failure of turbomachinery components. Classical numerical approaches to predict flutter rely on computationally expensive transient CFD simulations. In this work, a novel approach based on Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) is presented to enable efficient prediction of aerodynamic damping, and therefore flutter onset, in compressor rotor blades. A parametric blade design framework was developed to generate a set of rotor blade geometries based on aerodynamic and geometric input parameters. For each design, steady-state and transient CFD simulations were performed to provide input data for the GNN in combination with structural information from structural analyses. The trained model shows good agreement with CFD reference data, achieving high predictive accuracy with a limited dataset. The results demonstrate that GNNs offer a powerful tool for rapid flutter assessment, significantly reducing computational effort compared to conventional approaches.

Keywords: Aeroelasticity, flutter, axial compressor, CFD, aerodynamic damping, machine learning

Nomenclature

A	Area [m ²]
a	Vibration Amplitude [m]
c	Chord [m]
f	Frequency [Hz]
$h_v^{(l)}$	Embedding of node v at layer l [-]
k	Reference value [-]
\hat{k}	Model prediction [-]
K_E	Kinetic energy [Nm]

\dot{m}	Mass flow rate [kg/s]
N	Rotational speed [rpm]
n	Number of samples [-]
p	Pressure [Pa]
T	Temperature [K]
t	Time [s]
T_U	Turbulence intensity [-]
W^l	Trainable weight matrix at layer l [-]
W_{cycle}	Aerodynamic work per cycle [Nm]
η_s	Isentropic efficiency [-]
Π	Total-to-total pressure ratio [-]
σ	Inter-blade phase angle [°]
τ	Period of one vibration cycle [s]
φ	Activation function [-]
ζ_a	Aerodynamic damping coefficient [-]
$\mathcal{N}(v)$	Neighborhood of node v [-]
CFD	Computational fluid dynamics
FE	Finite elements
FiLM	Feature-wise linear modulation
FSI	Fluid-structure interaction
GNN	Graph neural network
HB	Harmonic balance
IBPA	Inter-blade phase angle
MAE	Mean absolute error
ML	Machine learning
MSE	Mean squared error
OP	Operating point
RANS	Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes
RMSE	Root mean squared error
SST	Shear-stress transport

1 INTRODUCTION

Flutter of turbomachinery components is a self-excited aeroelastic instability that occurs due to the interaction between unsteady aerodynamic forces and the natural blade vibration modes. Energy transferred from the fluid causes the blade excitation amplitudes to grow, potentially leading to high-cycle fatigue and structural damage of the blades. The continuous pursuit of fuel efficiency has led to lightweight yet highly loaded fan and compressor blades, which, as a result, are inherently more prone to flutter.

Therefore, reliable flutter prediction is essential in the design process of fan, compressor and turbine blades. Numerical flutter analysis methods are generally classified into classical methods, which correspond to one-way fluid-structure interaction (FSI) and do not consider the feedback from structural motion to fluid flow, and coupled methods, which implement two-way FSI, considering the interaction between the flow and the structure. Casoni et al. [1] review the most common computational methods for turbomachinery aeroelasticity, highlighting their respective advantages and limitations. Due to the high computational cost of directly coupled methods, the energy method proposed by Carta [2], which evaluates the aerodynamic work over one vibration cycle, has become a widely used standard approach for flutter prediction in turbomachinery components. During the design process, this method must be applied to multiple structural modes and inter-blade phase angles (IBPAs), as well as across a range of reduced frequencies, which again leads to considerable simulation effort and computation time.

Given the significant computational effort required by the previously mentioned methods to evaluate the aerodynamic damping and thus predict flutter, deep learning approaches are gaining attention as a promising strategy to accelerate computationally expensive aeroelastic analyses. In recent years, machine learning techniques have become increasingly important in turbomachinery research, for example in the areas of blade optimization [3], flow field prediction [4] and predictive maintenance [5]. Furthermore, methods of ML have also been applied to improve turbulence modeling in RANS-based CFD solvers ([6], [7]).

Moreover, neural networks have been successfully employed to predict the onset of flutter in aircraft wings [8], demonstrating the potential of data-driven approaches for aeroelastic stability prediction.

Building on these results, recent studies have explored machine learning methods specifically for aeroelastic turbomachinery applications. For instance, Liu et al. [9] developed a fast prediction model based on a GNN, that predicts the flow field and flutter stability of two-dimensional oscillating blade profiles. This approach leads to a significant reduction of computational time while offering reliable aeroelastic stability predictions. Bruni et al. [10] applied convolutional and feedforward neural networks to predict forced response vibrations in an industrial axial compressor based. Rauseo et al. [11] combined reduced-order mod-

eling with a neural network to predict stall flutter stability in turbomachinery blades.

In the present work, an application of a GNN framework is proposed for flutter prediction of three-dimensional axial compressor rotor blades. The model receives as input flow features on the blade surface derived from a steady-state CFD simulation, along with blade mode shapes and frequencies obtained from finite elements (FE) modal analyses. Based on these data, the GNN predicts the aerodynamic damping across specified operating conditions, providing a fast and reliable alternative to traditional flutter stability evaluation methods based on transient simulations.

2 METHODOLOGY

The methodology of this work integrates blade design, numerical simulations, and the developed neural network into a framework for fast flutter prediction in axial compressors. First, the parametric blade design procedure for generating the dataset used to train the GNN is presented. Subsequently, the numerical methods employed for CFD and FE analyses are described, followed by the energy method applied for aerodynamic damping evaluation. Finally, the architecture and training of the GNN model used for flutter prediction are outlined.

2.1 Blade Design

To generate a sufficient number of compressor rotor blade geometries required for GNN training, a parametric blade design framework was developed. Based on input parameters, such as design pressure ratio, mass flow, hub-to-tip ratio, Mach number, chord, thickness and number of blades, rotor blades are generated from NACA 65-series airfoils, incorporating radial equilibrium. First, the thermodynamic states at the rotor inlet and exit are calculated along with the flow velocities and angles at the mean blade radius. The spanwise distribution of flow velocities and flow angles is then determined using the free vortex design method, as described by Cohen et al. [12]. The blades are designed for a specified design point, while correlations for design deviation according to Johnson and Bullock [13] are taken into account to ensure consistent aerodynamic behavior beyond the nominal operating condition.

The resulting two-dimensional profiles are then staggered according to the determined flow angles and stacked along the span to form the three-dimensional blade geometry. Figure 1 illustrates exemplary profiles at hub, tip and mid-span, highlighting the variation of camber and blade twist along the span. An example of a three-dimensional blade consisting of seven stacked profiles is presented in Figure 2. To simplify both the blade design process and subsequent numerical analyses, no explicit blade-disk connection is modeled. Instead, all rotors are represented as blisks (integrally bladed rotors). This assumption removes the complexity associated with mechanical joints while

FIGURE 1: Blade profiles at hub, tip and mid-span

providing a consistent basis for the aerodynamic and structural evaluations.

The framework allows flexible variation of all design parameters, enabling the generation of a wide range of rotor blade geometries. These geometries subsequently serve as input for steady-state and transient CFD simulations and modal analyses, forming the basis of the dataset used for GNN training.

FIGURE 2: Three-dimensional rotor blade

2.2 Numerical Methods

The numerical simulations are performed using Ansys CFX as the flow solver, which solves the unsteady three-dimensional RANS equations in their conservation form. A structured mesh of the blade passage with HOH topology is generated using Ansys TurboGrid. The mesh resolution, including the number of cells and choice of y^+ for near-wall resolution, is determined based on a mesh independence study presented in Chapter 3.

All simulations assume fully turbulent flow, with turbulence closure provided by Menter's $k-\omega$ SST model [14]. A high-resolution scheme is applied for advection and turbulence numerics. The inlet boundary conditions prescribe the total pressure and total temperature, while the outlet is defined by a specified mass flow. Periodic boundary conditions are applied in circumferential direction, and no-slip conditions are applied at the hub, shroud and blade surfaces. The shroud is modeled as a counter-rotating wall to account for its relative motion with respect to the rotor.

Steady-state RANS simulations are carried out first, both to provide input data for the training of the GNN and to generate initial flow conditions for the subsequent unsteady flutter simulations. Convergence of the steady-state simulations is monitored using the RMS of the residuals, with a target value of $1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ for all governing equations.

The transient flutter simulations are performed using the Harmonic Balance (HB) approach ([15], [16]), a frequency-domain method for simulating unsteady periodic flows. Instead of directly solving the RANS equations in the time domain, the flow is represented by a Fourier series, which leads to a significant reduction of computational cost. In this study, three harmonics are chosen to capture the unsteady flow physics. To avoid expensive full-annulus simulations, the transient blade row method ([17], [18]) is applied, requiring only two passages to be simulated while still accounting for blade passing periodicity.

The modal analyses are performed using Ansys Mechanical to identify the mode shapes and natural frequencies of the blades. A linear elastic isotropic material model is assumed, with properties corresponding to polyethylene. This choice is not intended to represent realistic rotor behavior but rather to provoke early flutter onset for the generation of training data. Within this study, mechanical damping was neglected. In this study, only the first bending and first torsion mode, as shown in Figure 3, were investigated as these are most relevant for flutter onset in turbomachinery.

The resulting mode shapes are scaled to a vibration amplitude of approximately 0.5% of the chord length. The corresponding mesh displacements are then exported to Ansys CFX and imposed as periodic excitations of the blade surface at multiple IBPAs, from which the aerodynamic damping is subsequently evaluated.

FIGURE 3: Mode 1F (left) and 1T (right)

2.3 Aerodynamic Damping Evaluation using the Energy Method

A widely used approach to assess flutter stability and calculate the aerodynamic damping in turbomachinery components is the energy method which was originally formulated by Carta [2]. The basis of the energy method is the evaluation of the aerodynamic work performed by the unsteady aerodynamic forces on the vibrating blade surface. The aerodynamic work per vibration cycle can be determined as:

$$W_{cycle} = \int_{t_0}^{t_0+\tau} \int_A p \vec{v} \cdot \hat{n} dA dt, \quad (1)$$

where p is the fluid pressure, v the blade velocity due to the imposed vibrational displacements, \hat{n} is the surface normal unit vector, and A is the blade surface area.

In practice, the surface integral of the aerodynamic work is evaluated in discrete form over all mesh nodes on the blade surface, using the unsteady pressure distribution obtained from the CFD simulation.

A positive aerodynamic work indicates a net transfer of energy from the structure to the fluid, corresponding to stable behavior and damped vibrations. Conversely, a negative aerodynamic work indicates energy extraction from the fluid, resulting in a negative damping and the onset of flutter.

For each investigated mode and IBPA, the aerodynamic damping coefficient is computed by normalizing the aerodynamic work per cycle with the modal kinetic energy K_E of the blade:

$$\zeta_a = \frac{W_{cycle}}{4\pi K_E}. \quad (2)$$

The modal kinetic energy is defined as:

$$K_E = \frac{1}{2} M \omega^2 a^2, \quad (3)$$

with M denoting the modal mass, ω the angular frequency, and a the vibration amplitude of the respective mode.

2.4 Graph Neural Network

A Graph Neural Network (GNN) architecture is employed as the deep learning model for aerodynamic damping prediction. GNNs are particularly well-suited for data that can be represented as graphs. This is especially beneficial for applications using numerical data which is usually non-Euclidean in nature. The architecture of the proposed GNN is illustrated in Figure 4. The deep learning model was implemented in Python using the PyTorch framework. Each node, corresponding to a physical location (x, y, z) of the blade surface, is associated with flow field parameters derived from the steady-state simulation. These including force, Mach number, total pressure, total temperature, velocity, wall shear, and mesh displacement. Together they form the node-level graph attributes. Additionally, design-specific features, such as IBPA, blade count, vibration frequency, maximum vibration amplitude, rotational speed and hub-to-tip ratio are incorporated as global parameters.

Node-level as well as global feature are scaled to the range [0,1] using min-max normalization, with minimum and maximum values determined from the training dataset.

In order to improve the robustness of the model and mitigate overfitting, Gaussian noise is added to the normalized node-level features during training. The noise magnitude is controlled by a standard deviation parameter, σ_{noise} , and can be gradually reduced over the course of training according to a linear scheduler. This approach simulates slight perturbations in the input features and encourages the network to learn more generalized representations, thereby enhancing predictive reliability on unseen configurations. To effectively combine global parameters with node-level embeddings, Feature-wise Linear Modulation (FiLM) layers [19] are employed. In the FiLM approach, the global features are passed through a small neural network to generate scaling and shifting coefficients, which are then applied to the node embeddings at each layer.

GraphSAGE [20] is used for neighborhood sampling and feature aggregation. Unlike transductive embedding approaches, GraphSAGE learns an inductive aggregation function that can generalize to previously unseen graphs. For each layer l , the embedding of a node v is calculated as:

$$\mathbf{h}_v^{(l)} = \varphi \left(W^{(l)} \cdot \left[\mathbf{h}_v^{(l-1)} \parallel \frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}(v)|} \sum_{u \in \mathcal{N}(v)} \mathbf{h}_u^{(l-1)} \right] \right), \quad (4)$$

where $\mathcal{N}(v)$ is the set of neighbors of v , $W^{(l)}$ is a trainable weight matrix, \parallel denotes concatenation, and φ is the activation function, chosen here as Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU). After

FIGURE 4: Schematic architecture of the GNN for aerodynamic damping prediction

each GraphSAGE layer, the node embeddings are re-normalized to the range $[0,1]$ to stabilize the training and ensure consistent feature scaling across layers.

The resulting node embeddings are pooled into a single graph-level representation using global mean pooling. This pooled embedding is then concatenated with the global design parameters and passed through fully connected layers to predict the aerodynamic damping coefficient. The network is trained to perform regression on the aerodynamic damping coefficient, predicting continuous values. The final dense layers output the aerodynamic damping prediction, and the network is trained end-to-end using the AdamW optimizer [21] with SmoothL1Loss [22], which combines the benefits of L1 and L2 loss calculation and is defined as:

$$L(\hat{k}, k) = \begin{cases} 0.5(\hat{k}_i - k_i)^2 & \text{if } |\hat{k}_i - k_i| \leq 1, \\ |\hat{k}_i - k_i| - 0.5 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

To evaluate the predictive performance of the model, standard error metrics are applied. The mean absolute error (MAE) and the root mean squared error (RMSE) quantify the magnitude of prediction errors, while the coefficient of determination (R^2) measures the proportion of variance in the target data explained by

the model:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |k_i - \hat{k}_i|, \quad (6)$$

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (k_i - \hat{k}_i)^2}, \quad (7)$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (k_i - \hat{k}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (k_i - \bar{k})^2}, \quad (8)$$

where k_i are the reference values, \hat{k}_i the model predictions, \bar{k} the mean of the reference values, and n the number of samples.

3 NUMERICAL SETUP

In this study, all simulations were performed for the rotor only. Both steady-state and transient simulations were carried out to provide the necessary input data for the GNN training. Two operating points were considered: the design point and an off-design condition at approximately 85% of the design mass flow. A mesh independence study to ensure reliable CFD results was carried out for the reference blade, which is based on the rotor of the CATAO test rig, which is a vertical 1.5-stage axial compressor, located at Chair of Aero Engines at TU Berlin (see Figure 5). Numerical simulations of the full compressor stage geometry had been validated against experimental measurements previously, but in the present study only the rotor is simulated. The boundary conditions for the reference simulation were derived from experimental measurements and are summarized in

FIGURE 5: CATAO compressor test rig

Tab. 1. Total pressure and total temperature were specified at the inlet, while the outlet was defined by the prescribed mass flow.

TABLE 1: Boundary conditions for the steady-state simulation of the CATAO blade geometry

	$p_{t,in}$	$T_{t,in}$	\dot{m}_{out}	T_U	N
REF	101880 Pa	291 K	2.15 kg/s	5%	2397 rpm

For the steady-state simulations, characteristic results of four different meshes (M1 to M4) with different number of cells were compared. Figure 6 show the total-to-total pressure ratio Π and isentropic efficiency η_s , respectively, as a function of the total number of cells. Both quantities were normalized with respect to the values obtained for mesh M3. The pressure ratio Π remained nearly constant for meshes M2 to M4, while the isentropic efficiency showed a small decrease with increasing cell count in this range. Additionally, the blade loading for these meshes was compared and is shown in Figure 7. It exhibited noticeable differences for meshes M1 and M2 compared to M3 and M4, whereas the latter two yielded almost identical pressure distributions. Therefore, M3 was selected as the final mesh, providing the best compromise between numerical accuracy and computational cost. With a cell count of approximately 3,000,000 cells and an average y^+ of 0.7, the boundary layer was sufficiently resolved to ensure accurate near-wall resolution when using the $k-\omega$ -SST turbulence model. The meshing of the different blade designs was carried out using the same mesh settings resulting in similar mesh qualities. The mesh of the steady-state single-passage including the boundary layer refinement is presented in Figure 8

For the transient flutter simulations, the inlet and outlet sections

(a) Isentropic efficiency η_s

(b) Total pressure ratio Π

FIGURE 6: Mesh independence study: Comparison of efficiency and pressure ratio for four different meshes

FIGURE 7: Comparison of pressure distribution on the blade surface at 50% span for four different meshes

of the passage were shortened in order to reduce the computational effort, resulting in a mesh size of approximately 650,000 elements. A comparison against the full-domain case confirmed that the reduced mesh reproduces the aerodynamic damping in good agreement, thereby ensuring good accuracy at significantly lower computational cost. The boundary conditions were extracted from the steady-state simulations. The mesh of the transient passages is shown in Figure 9 for the reference blade.

4 FLUTTER PREDICTION USING A GNN

This chapter presents the results and discussion of applying GNNs to the prediction of aerodynamic damping in compressor

FIGURE 8: Mesh M3 of the steady-state passage

FIGURE 9: Mesh of the transient passages

rotor blades and compares the predictions with CFD reference data. First, the input features derived from CFD and FE simulations, as well as the preprocessing steps required to prepare them as suitable GNN input, are described. Subsequently, the performance of the GNN model during training and validation is evaluated based on loss convergence, error metrics, and classification accuracy. Finally, the trained model is applied to different test cases in order to evaluate its predictive capability and the potential of GNNs for rapid and reliable flutter assessment.

4.1 Feature Engineering and Data Preparation

In total, four rotor configurations at two operating points were simulated, resulting in a dataset of 708 samples when considering the first bending and torsion modes together with mul-

tle IBPAs. The input features described in Section 2.4 were extracted from the corresponding blade designs and steady-state CFD simulations, while structural information in the form of mode shapes and natural frequencies obtained from FE simulations was incorporated. Since the FE mesh differs from the CFD mesh, the modal displacements were interpolated onto the CFD surface mesh using linear interpolation within the convex hull and inverse distance weighting outside, ensuring compatibility of the structural data with the graph representation. The target variable for each sample was the aerodynamic damping coefficient obtained from transient flutter simulations. Additionally, the global parameters listed in Section 2.4 were extracted from the designs and CFD results and included in the dataset. All features were normalized to the range $[0,1]$ to ensure comparable scales and stable network training.

To enlarge the training dataset without performing a large number of computational intensive transient flutter simulations, the obtained training data was artificially extended. The aerodynamic damping was calculated for a limited number of specified IBPAs and then interpolated on the full range between -180° and 180° . Figure 10 provides a comparison between the damping curve obtained from 41 computed IBPAs with their corresponding damping coefficients and the interpolated curve based on only 16 supporting points. To improve the accuracy at lower IBPAs, where flutter is most likely to occur, a denser distribution of CFD data was used in this region, while larger spacing was applied towards $\pm 180^\circ$. The interpolation shows only small deviations from the calculated curve, primarily near the boundary regions around -180° and 180° , while reducing the computational effort by more than half and still capturing the overall trend and characteristic features of the damping distribution with high fidelity.

FIGURE 10: Comparison of damping curves from CFD and interpolated data

4.2 Model Training and Validation

The GNN was trained on the prepared dataset consisting of 708 sample graphs, which were randomly split into training, validation and test set at the ratio of 80:10:10. Each graph comprised nodal and global features that together represented one blade geometry in combination with a single structural mode, a single operating point, and one IBPA. Due to memory constraints, the batch size was limited to 1. The architecture consisted of three GraphSAGE layers with 128 hidden units each, followed by fully connected layers for regression. The hyperparameters which were used for the training are summarized in Table 2. The learning rate (LR) was initially set to 0.001 and subsequently adapted during training using a learning rate scheduler to improve convergence stability. A weight decay of $1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ was applied in the AdamW optimizer to regularize the training and mitigate overfitting. Dropout regularization was not applied, as preliminary studies showed that including dropout led to underfitting and degraded the predictive performance of the model. In addition, early stopping was employed to prevent overfitting and ensure robust generalization.

Figure 11 shows the SmoothL1Loss curves for training and val-

FIGURE 11: Training and validation loss curves of the GNN

ited range of operating conditions and geometrical variations. As a result, the reported metrics primarily reflect the model’s performance within this domain, and may not directly translate to cases that are significantly different from the training data.

Figure 12 shows the comparison of predicted damping coeffi-

TABLE 2: Hyperparameters used for the training of the GNN

LR	Batch size	Layers	Hidden channels
0.001	1	3	128

validation over the training epochs. The loss curves indicate a convergence of the model after approximately 150 epochs, with the lower training loss compared to the validation loss pointing to slight overfitting. Furthermore, the stable behavior of the curves underlines the effectiveness of the adaptive learning rate and early stopping strategy applied during training. The predictive performance of the trained model was assessed using standard error metrics, including MAE, RMSE and R^2 . The R^2 value of 0.99 indicates that nearly all of the variance in the target data was captured by the model. The RMSE and MAE values of 0.003 and 0.002, respectively, are small and closely aligned, indicating consistent performance across the dataset and suggesting that errors are not dominated by large outliers. While these values indicate very good agreement between model predictions and the CFD reference data, it should be noted that the CFD simulations themselves are subject to modeling and discretization uncertainties. Consequently, the reported prediction errors should be interpreted in the context of these inherent CFD uncertainties, rather than as absolute deviations from the true physical values. Moreover, the dataset used for training and validation represents a lim-

TABLE 3: Error metrics: MAE, RMSE and R^2

MAE	RMSE	R^2
0.002	0.003	0.99

cients and CFD evaluated damping coefficients on the test split, where the dashed line represents the ideal correlation. It shows that the model predictions are in very close agreement with the simulated data. The points are closely aligned along the diagonal, indicating that no systematic over- or underprediction occurs. This underlines the ability of the model to reproduce the aerodynamic damping values with high accuracy across the investigated parameter space. To evaluate the model’s ability to classify stability, the predicted aerodynamic damping values were transformed into a binary classification problem: negative damping values were assigned to the unstable class (flutter), and positive values to the stable class (no flutter). The resulting confusion matrix shown in Figure 13 demonstrates that all cases in the test set were correctly classified. While such a result highlights the strong discriminative capability of the model, it should also be noted that the dataset is limited to the investigated design space. Therefore, the performance outside this range cannot be inferred directly.

FIGURE 12: Comparison of predicted damping coefficients from the GNN against reference CFD values

FIGURE 13: Confusion Matrix of the GNN training

4.3 Application to Representative Test Cases

To assess the predictive capability and generalizability of the trained GNN, the model was applied to test cases beyond the training data, and the predicted damping behavior was compared to CFD results. Two scenarios were considered. First, the GNN was evaluated on an unseen blade geometry to examine its ability to generalize to new structural and aerodynamic configurations. The input features were constructed in the same way as for model training (see Section 4.2), i.e. based on the results from steady-state CFD simulations and FE modal analyses. Additionally, a list of IBPAs is provided, for which the damping is predicted. Using the trained GNN and the scaling factors obtained during training, the aerodynamic damping values can be directly predicted for the specified configurations.

Notably, the design variables of this configuration lie outside the

range of values present in the training dataset. A comparison of the predicted damping coefficients with the CFD evaluated results is presented in Figure 14. The predicted damping deviates substantially from the CFD reference values in terms of absolute magnitude. In particular, the damping is significantly overpredicted across the entire IBPA range. These results indicate that the current model is not yet capable of generalizing to new blade geometries, emphasizing the necessity of expanding and diversifying the training dataset. Second, a blade geometry, which

FIGURE 14: Comparison of GNN-predicted and CFD-evaluated damping coefficients for the CATAO geometry at an untrained geometry

was previously used for the training, was analyzed at an operating point not included in the training set. For this purpose, the CATAO reference blade geometry was analyzed at an unseen operating point. The aerodynamic damping coefficients were then evaluated for both the first bending mode and the first torsion mode.

Figure 15 presents a comparison between the GNN-predicted damping coefficients and CFD simulated reference damping for the first bending mode. In contrast to the previous test case, the prediction show noticeably improved prediction accuracy, with maximum deviations of -13% at an IBPA of 90°. Both the absolute level of the damping and the characteristic variation across the IBPA range are captured with significantly higher accuracy compared to the previous case. The largest discrepancies occur at positive IBPAs between approximately 45° and 120°, while the damping coefficients at negative IBPAs are generally reproduced well. The closest agreement between predicted and simulated damping coefficients occurs at an IBPA of -45°, with a deviation of only 0.2%. Overall, the predicted levels of aerodynamic damping are slightly higher than the CFD results for negative IBPAs and generally lower for positive IBPAs, with the exception at 180°, where the prediction is higher than the CFD

FIGURE 15: Comparison of GNN-predicted and CFD-evaluated damping coefficients for the CATAO geometry at an untrained operating point for the first bending mode (1F)

reference value. The prediction results for the same geometry and operating point for the first torsion mode are presented in Figure 16. Similar to the first bending mode, the overall damping trend is well reproduced, while the maximum relative deviation is slightly larger. Thus, the curve reflects correct tendencies in terms of qualitative behaviors, such as identifying the most critical IBPAs. The maximum deviation of -45% occurs at an IBPA of 90°. In this case, the GNN consistently underpredicts the damping, which, while indicating a model limitation in terms of accuracy, can be considered advantageous for conservative stability prediction. For both cases, it can also be observed that the largest deviations occur at IBPAs around 90°.

In summary, the applications of the GNN demonstrate its capability to capture overall damping trends. However, noticeable deviations from the simulated values remain, indicating that additional training data is required to achieve more accurate predictions.

5 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In this work, a GNN approach was presented for the prediction of aerodynamic damping, enabling a fast analysis of flutter behavior of compressor blades. Compared to conventional CFD-based methods, the proposed approach enables the prediction of aerodynamic damping over the full range of IBPAs based on steady-state CFD results and modal information as input data, while significantly reducing the required computation time.

The results of the model training and application to test cases demonstrate that the proposed method enables flutter prediction in principle. For blade geometries included in the training dataset, the GNN is able to reproduce damping behavior at OPs not seen during training with good accuracy, even when trained on a very limited dataset of numerical results. This capability

FIGURE 16: Comparison of GNN-predicted and CFD-evaluated damping coefficients for the CATAO geometry at an untrained operating point for the first torsion mode (1T)

is of significant practical relevance, as it allows for an efficient assessment of off-design behavior, providing aeroelastic stability information at a fraction of the computational cost of conventional methods. At the same time, the study shows that the current models does not yet generalize reliably to unseen blade geometries. When applied to a new configuration, the predicted damping deviated substantially in magnitude from high-fidelity CFD results, even though some qualitative tendencies were already captured. These findings underline the need to expand and diversify the training dataset in order to improve generalizability and enable robust flutter prediction across a wider range of geometries and flow conditions. In addition, systematic hyperparameter optimization is recommended, as the selection of hyperparameters has a significant influence on the efficiency of the training process as well as on the predictive accuracy and robustness of the model. The GNN-based method substantially reduces computational cost compared to classical approaches using transient CFD simulations, offering a practical tool for early-stage design evaluations. However, it should be noted that the model's predictive quality is inherently limited by the accuracy of the underlying training data obtained from CFD and FE simulations, and systematic errors in the simulations may propagate through the predictions. Although the trained GNN provides aerodynamic damping predictions in just a few seconds, the initial training process is computationally intensive, and incorporating additional training data would further increase the required time. To maintain efficiency and scalability, the framework is designed to allow modular updates with new data. To make the integration of new data more efficient and improve model performance, a sensitivity analysis of the input features should be conducted to identify the parameters with the greatest influence on the network's predictions. Future work should initially focus on expanding the training dataset, which is essential for improving

the generalizability of the GNN. In this context, additional data could be obtained not only from numerical simulations, but also from experimental measurements or existing legacy datasets, further enhancing the model’s applicability. Furthermore, the approach could be extended by incorporating predictions of flow fields and mode shapes, providing a unified framework for flutter assessment while maintaining low computational cost. Such an integrated framework is particularly suitable for automated blade optimization workflows, enabling rapid evaluation of aeroelastic stability during early stages of the design process. Overall, the present study demonstrates that GNNs represent a powerful and efficient tool for fast and reliable flutter prediction in axial compressors.

REFERENCES

- [1] Casoni, M., and Benini, E., 2021. “A Review of Computational Methods and Reduced Order Models for Flutter Prediction in Turbomachinery”. *Aerospace*, **8**(9), Sept.
- [2] Carta, F. O., 1967. “Coupled Blade-Disk-Shroud Flutter Instabilities in Turbojet Engine Rotors”. *Journal of Engineering for Power*, **89**(3), July, pp. 419–426.
- [3] Zhang, C., and Janeway, M., 2022. “Optimization of Turbine Blade Aerodynamic Designs Using CFD and Neural Network Models”. *International Journal of Turbomachinery, Propulsion and Power*, **7**(3), June, p. 20.
- [4] Bruni, G., Maleki, S., and Krishnababu, S. K., 2024. “C(NN)FD - A Deep Learning Framework for Turbomachinery CFD Analysis”. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, **20**(8), Aug., pp. 10230–10237.
- [5] Sepe, M., Graziano, A., Badora, M., Di Stazio, A., Bellani, L., Compare, M., and Zio, E., 2021. “A Physics-Informed Machine Learning Framework for Predictive Maintenance Applied to Turbomachinery Assets”. *Journal of the Global Power and Propulsion Society*(May), May, pp. 1–15.
- [6] Hammond, J., Pepper, N., Montomoli, F., and Michelassi, V., 2022. “Machine Learning Methods in CFD for Turbomachinery: A Review”. *International Journal of Turbomachinery, Propulsion and Power*, **7**(2), May, p. 16.
- [7] Fesquet, J., Bauerheim, M., Rojda, L., Bousquet, Y., and Binder, N., 2025. “Application of Deep Learning for Fan Rotor Blade Performance Prediction in Turbomachinery”. *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **147**(11), May, p. 11.
- [8] Pitt, D., and Haudrich, D., 2005. “Development of an Artificial Neural Aeroelastic Network (AN²) for the Prediction of Multiple Flutter Crossing”. In 46th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference, American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics.
- [9] Liu, Y., Li, Y., Li, L., Xie, Y., and Zhang, D., 2024. “A Fast Prediction Model of Blade Flutter in Turbomachinery Based on Graph Convolutional Neural Network”. *Aerospace Science and Technology*, **148**, May, p. 109119.
- [10] Bruni, G., Krishnababu, S., and Jackson, S., 2022. “Application of Machine Learning to Forced Response Predictions of an Industrial Axial Compressor Rotor Blade”. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, **145**(1), Oct., pp. 1–11.
- [11] Rauseo, M., Zhao, F., and Vahdati, M., 2024. “Physics Guided Machine Learning Modelling of Compressor Stall Flutter”. *Journal of the Global Power and Propulsion Society*, **8**, Aug., pp. 295–309.
- [12] Cohen, H., Rogers, G. F. C., and Saravanamuttoo, H. I. H., 2000. *Gas Turbine Theory*, 4th ed. Prentice Hall, Harlow.
- [13] Johnson, I. A., and Bullock, R. O., 1965. Aerodynamic Design of Axial Flow Compressors. Tech. Rep. NASA-SP-36, NASA Lewis Research Center.
- [14] Menter, F. R., 1994. “Two-Equation Eddy-Viscosity Turbulence Models for Engineering Applications”. *AIAA Journal*, **32**(8), Aug., pp. 1598–1605.
- [15] Hall, K. C., Thomas, J. P., and Clark, W. S., 2002. “Computation of Unsteady Nonlinear Flows in Cascades Using a Harmonic Balance Technique”. *AIAA Journal*, **40**(5), May, pp. 879–886.
- [16] Gopinath, A., and Jameson, A., 2005. “Time Spectral Method for Periodic Unsteady Computations over Two- and Three-Dimensional Bodies”. In 43rd AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting and Exhibit, AIAA.
- [17] He, L., 1990. “An Euler Solution for Unsteady Flows Around Oscillating Blades”. *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **112**(4), Oct., pp. 714–722.
- [18] Gerolymos, G. A., Michon, G. J., and Neubauer, J., 2002. “Analysis and Application of Chorochronic Periodicity in Turbomachinery Rotor/Stator Interaction Computations”. *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, **18**(6), Nov., pp. 1139–1152.
- [19] Perez, E., Strub, F., De Vries, H., Dumoulin, V., and Courville, A., 2018. “FiLM: Visual Reasoning with a General Conditioning Layer”. *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, **32**(1), Apr., pp. 11671–11678.
- [20] Hamilton, W. L., Ying, R., and Leskovec, J., 2017. Inductive Representation Learning on Large Graphs.
- [21] Loshchilov, I., and Hutter, F., 2019. “Decoupled Weight Decay Regularization”. In 7th International Conference on Learning Representations, ICLR 2019, New Orleans, LA, USA, May 6-9, 2019.
- [22] Girshick, R., 2015. “Fast R-CNN”. In 2015 IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV), IEEE, pp. 1440–1448.